

Preserving Situating Practices

– BDCAM 2025, SAS University of London, Adrian Demleitner

Engaging Critically with Source Code

– *"Critical Code Studies"*, Mark Marino (2020)

- Ideological Underbelly
- Theoretical Foundations
- Methodology and Case

**Preservation
Is Political**

Situatedness

– *"Situated Knowledges: The Science Question in Feminism and the Privilege of Partial Perspective"*, Donna Haraway (1988)

Privileged Bodies

– Privileged bodies refer to those who occupy positions of power and centrality in society, often benefiting from historical, social, and cultural structures that grant them advantages over others.

– Roberta Williams. "A Pedestal, A Table, A Love Letter", Laine Nooney (2013)

Thick Assemblages* of Situated Practices

– * as outlined by Jane Bennett (2010), Anna Tsing (2015), and Heather Wiltse (2020)

– “Assembling Auras”, Dany Guy-Bélanger (2022) [model illustrated by author]

– “Preserving Situated Practices”, Adrian Demleitner (2024)

```

$C000 $4C $98 $C1   JMP $C198
-----
$C003 $4C $21 $C3   JMP $C321
-----
[...]
-----
$C021 $A9 $00         LDA #$00
$C023 $8D $B2 $02   STA $02B2
$C026 $AD $AE $02   LDA $02AE
$C029 $D0 $3F         BNE $C06A
$C02B $20 $FD $AE   JSR $AEFD
$C02E $20 $9E $AD   JSR $AD9E
$C031 $20 $A3 $B6   JSR $B6A3
$C034 $C9 $00         CMP #$00
$C036 $D0 $06         BNE $C03E
$C038 $A9 $FF         LDA #$FF
$C03A $8D $AD $02   STA $02AD
$C03D $60           RTS
-----
[...]
-----

```

```

$C09B $20 $A1 $C0   JSR $C0A1
$C09E $4C $78 $C0   JMP $C078
-----
$C0A1 $20 $36 $C2   JSR $C236
$C0A4 $20 $3A $C2   JSR $C23A
$C0A7 $C9 $00         CMP #$00
$C0A9 $D0 $F6         BNE $C0A1
$C0AB $60           RTS
-----
$C09B $20 $A1 $C0   JSR $C0A1
$C09E $4C $78 $C0   JMP $C078
-----
$C0A1 $20 $36 $C2   JSR $C236
$C0A4 $20 $3A $C2   JSR $C23A
$C0A7 $C9 $00         CMP #$00
$C0A9 $D0 $F6         BNE $C0A1
$C0AB $60           RTS

```

[Continued...]


```

READY.
LIST 50000-50050

50000 :
50005 IF UD THEN SYSSB:GOTO50100
50010 POKE198,0:BE$="":PRINT:PRINT">";
50020 POKE204,0:WAIT198,255:GETX$
50035 POKE204,1:XA=ASC(X$):L=LEN(BE$)
50040 IF(XA=13ANDL>0)THENPRINT" ":GOTO50
090
50042 IFXA=136THENVE=22:G1=0:OB=0:PE=0:P
RINT" ":RETURN
50043 IFXA=135THENVE=24:RETURN
50045 IFXA=133THENPRINT" □":GOSUB54000:F
=0:GOTO50010
50046 IFXA=134THENIFER<>255ANDVE<>0THENP
RINTCHR$(34):RETURN
50047 IFXA<>19ANDXA<>147THEN50050
50049 GOSUB53000:GOTO50010
50050 IFXA=20ANDLTHEN PRINT"|| |";:BE$=
LEFT$(BE$,LEN(BE$)-1):GOTO50020

READY.

```

- VICE Emulator displaying BASIC listing of Robox (1986).

64'er

**Sonderheft
Abenteuerspiele**

SONDERHEFT 4/1986 Lit. 12.000/Std. 14,- DM 14,-

Markt & Technik

64'er

**So programmiert man
Abenteuerspiele
und künstliche
Intelligenz**

**Der Super-Kurs
zum Mitmachen**

- ★ mit vielen Beispiel-Listings zum Abtippen
- ★ Programmiertricks der Profis
- ★ So versteht ein Spiel mehr als 1000 Worte
- ★ Spiele ohne Speichergrenzen
- ★ So programmiert man Spiele, die denken, lernen und handeln

**Die besten
Abenteuerspiele
zum Abtippen**

**Alle Programme auch auf
Diskette erhältlich**

- Cover C64'er Sonderheft Abenteuerspiele (#4, 1986)

```

10 OPEN 1,8,3,"WORTSCHATZ":OPEN 15,8,15:RE
  M WORTSCHATZ-DATEI DEFFNEN <125>
20 DATA 1,3,0,28,31,47,51,60,68,0,70,76,0,
  82,90,93,100,101,116,149,155,158 <160>
30 DATA 178,0,0,189 <193>
35 DATA 198 :REM BUCHSTABE NACH Z !?! <235>
40 DIM IN(26):FOR I=0 TO 26:READ IN(I):NEX
  T I <193>
50 GOSUB 50000 <062>
60 PRINT"SN="SN:PRINT"VE="VE:PRINT"O1="O1:
  PRINT"O2="O2:PRINT"UD="UD:PRINT"RI="RI <017>
70 PRINT"AD="AD:PRINT:GOTO 50 <111>
50000 REM ***** <227>
50001 REM * * <009>
50002 REM * WORT-PARSER 4.0 * <169>
50003 REM * * <011>
50004 REM * <C> 1986 BEI * <086>
50005 REM * * <013>
50006 REM * MICHAEL NICKLES * <082>
50007 REM * * <015>
50008 REM ***** <235>
50010 REM BEFEHLSATZEINGABE -----
----- <069>
50011 : <202>
50012 IF UD>0 THEN 50500:REM UND <171>
50015 SL=80: REM BEFEHLSATZLAENGE <144>
50020 PRINT" {DOWN}":BE$="":POKE 198,0:POKE
  211,0:POKE 214,22:SYS 58732:PRINT" {
  YELLOW}"; <156>
50030 GET X$:IF PEEK(203)=1 THEN 50120 <226>
50040 IF X$="" THEN 50030 <171>
50050 IF LEN(BE$)=0 AND ASC(X$)=20 THEN 50
  030 <148>
50060 I=ASC(X$):IF I<32 OR I>133 AND I<159
  THEN IF I<>20 THEN 50030 <131>
50070 IF LEN(BE$)=SL AND I<>20 THEN 50030 <128>
50080 BE$=BE$+X$ <031>
50090 PRINT CHR$(20);X$;" "; <108>
51001 : <176>
51007 REM ANFANG UND ENDE DES SUCHBEREICHE
  S ERMITTELN <117>
51008 I=ASC(LEFT$(SU$,1)) <176>
51009 IF I-65<0 OR I-65>25 THEN GOSUB 5150
  0:GOTO 50000 <134>
51010 AN=IN(I-65):REM ANFANG DES SUCHBEREI
  CHES <164>
51012 IZ=64 <200>
51013 IF IN(I-IZ)=0 THEN IZ=IZ-1:GOTO 5101
  3 <086>
51015 EN=IN(I-IZ)-1:REM ENDE DES SUCHBEREI
  CHES <070>
51016 IF AN=0 THEN GOSUB 51500:UD=0:GOTO 5
  0000 <249>
51020 SZ=197:N=INT(LOG(EN-AN+1)/LOG(2))+1
  :REM MAXIMAL-FORMEL <121>
51030 SA=AN-1+(2^N)/2:REM MITTE DER GES.DA
  T <073>
51040 GOSUB 52100:REM A$ LESEN <234>
51050 N=N-1 :REM 1.ABFRAGE <045>
51060 : <235>
51070 REM SU$ MIT A$ VERGLEICHEN ----- <042>
51080 : IF LEN(SU$)<3 THEN 51110 <140>
51090 : IF WA=1 AND SU$=LEFT$(A$,LEN(SU$))
  THEN VE=WC:GOTO 51300 <157>
51100 : IF WA<>3 OR SU$<>RIGHT$(A$,LEN(SU$
  )) THEN 51110 <161>
51102 : IF UD=1 OR UD=2 THEN UD=3:O1=0:O2
  =0 <042>
51104 : IF O1=0 THEN O1=WC:OM=O1:GOTO 51
  300 <133>
51105 : IF O2=0 THEN O2=WC:OM=O1:GOTO 51
  300 <170>
51110 : IF WA=2 AND SU$=A$
  THEN RI=WC:GOTO 51300 <140>
51115 : IF WA=5 AND SU$=A$
  THEN AD=WC:GOTO 51300 <247>
51120 : IF WA=1 AND SU$=A$

```


Schweizer Mustermesse Basel

Tel. 061 26 20.20

Nach Load im
Programmmodus

E1B5 JSR A68E (Progzeiger auf Stack) ⁴²⁶³⁸
JSR A533 (Progzeiger neu binden) ⁴²²⁹¹
JMP ~~A677~~ (CLR) ⁴²⁶⁴⁵
JMP 4278d

MEMBOT FF9C 65436

CLC
LDX#
LDY#>
JSR MEMBOT

- ...handwritten notes with Assembly code

Oral History

Code Elicitation

[...]

Die Spielegrafiken werden mittels der Routine *SYS SL nachgeladen (Programmzeile 60020)*. Die *Variable Z2* bezeichnet dabei die Nummer eines Raums, einer Karte oder *(falls Z2 > 1000)* den Deathscreen. Der verwendete Komprimierungsmethode für die Grafikdateien ist übrigens recht simpel, eine hausgemachte Variante des *Run-length-Encoding (RLE)*.

[...continued]

- On-Court Tennis (1985) [Commodore 64]

Programming as a Directive Speech Act

– *“Humanities of the Digital.”* In *Digitale Schriftlichkeit: Programmieren, Prozessieren und Codieren von Schrift*, Stefan Höltgen (2024) – *“Gaming the Iron Curtain”*, Jaroslav Švelch (2018)

Family Struggles and Hidden Labor

Magic Moments and Becoming

– Laro Schatzer in front of his TI-99/4A setup

Video Game Development as Coming of Age Safe Spaces

– Robin François, from the Swiss Video Game Archivists, and me listening to the audio of a TI-99/4A cassette. Eléonore Bernard and Ralph Michel are off-picture.

– VICE emulator showing BASIC commands to dump source code.
Code, Oral History,

– Digital preservation setup with 5.25" floppy drive, a Pauline controller, and the original Robox (1986) floppies

Programming and Preservation as Situated Practices

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